

Use of Solar Photovoltaics for the Achievement of the National Goals for Energy and Climate in Greece

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ABSTRACT:

Solar photovoltaic technology grows rapid nowadays due to many advantages including the generation of low-cost electricity compared to other technologies. The Greek National Plan for Energy and Climate foresees that solar photovoltaic energy will have a pivotal role in the clean energy transition of the country. The energy generation from solar-PV systems in 2050 is foreseen to correspond at 32.47% of the electricity demand in Greece while the required land area for the installation of solar-PVs corresponds at 0.92% of the total area of the country. The installed power of solar photovoltaics in 2050 will correspond at 53.38% of the total installed power of renewable energy systems in Greece while the installed power of the power storage systems will correspond at 61.54% of the total installed power of solar-PVs. The majority of solar photovoltaic systems are nowadays installed either on the soil or on rooftops of buildings. However, more configurations for the installation of solar-PV systems are available including their installation in buildings' facades, on the surface of water reservoirs, vertically on the ground and on the soil allowing the co-production of electricity and food. New types of solar-PV modules have emerged and some of them are already used commercially. These include, semi-transparent photovoltaics, double-phase photovoltaics, agrivoltaics and organic photovoltaics. The role of several external factors affecting positively or negatively the growth of solar photovoltaic systems in Greece have been analyzed according to PESTEL methodology.

Keywords: energy, Greece, National plan, Pestel analysis, solar photovoltaics.

Suggested Citation: J. Vourdoubas, " Use of Solar Photovoltaics for the Achievement of the National Goals for Energy and Climate in Greece," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(5), pp. 4-15, Sep-Nov 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(5\).01](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(5).01)

INTRODUCTION

The development of solar photovoltaics (solar-PV) worldwide is rapid replacing the use of fossil fuels in power generation. Recent developments in solar-PV technology have increased the energy efficiency and decreased the capital cost of solar modules. Generation of solar-PV electricity is currently cheaper in many countries compared to power generation from fossil fuels. Therefore, it is foreseen that the role of solar cells is going to be pivotal in climate change mitigation and in the achievement of clean energy transition according to the international agreement signed in Paris in 2015 [1].

The solar irradiance in Greece is high and the electricity yield from solar modules is also high while the generation of solar-PV electricity is profitable without any subsidies. The Greek National Plan for Energy and Climate (NPEC) foresees that solar photovoltaics should have a primary role in the achievement of the net-zero carbon emissions target in Greece by 2050 [2]. Several types of solar modules in different configurations can be used for solar electricity generation [3], [4], [5], [6], [7]. The use of solar-PV systems for de-carbonizing the power sector in Greece in the coming decades could be affected from various external factors categorized as political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal [8], [9], [10].

The Aims of the Current Work are:

- a) To examine of the role of solar power in achieving the targets of carbon neutrality in Greece until 2050 according to roadmap proposed by the NPEC,
- b) To study of different types of solar modules which can be used in various configurations for electricity generation in Greece in the near future according to the NPEC, and
- c) To study of the impacts of several external factors on the development of solar-PV systems in Greece until 2050.

The text is structured as follows: After the literature survey the forecast of the Greek NPEC regarding the development of solar-PV systems during the period 2025-2050 is mentioned. In the following section various types of solar photovoltaic modules and different configurations that can be used for power generation in Greece are stated. Next, the impacts of several external factors in the development of solar photovoltaic systems in Greece until 2050 using PESTEL analysis are analyzed. The text ends with discussion of the findings, the conclusions drawn and the citation of the references used.

The work is innovative since there are not similar studies published so far for Greece while it covers an existing gap regarding the types and configurations of solar modules which could be used in the next decades in Greece achieving the green energy transition. It could be useful to policy makers, to local and regional authorities, as well as to energy companies and investors who are willing to invest in solar-PV systems in the country.

LITERATURE SURVEY

The climate and energy goals in northern and western Europe have been studied [1]. The authors stated that an efficient national policy mix for achieving the energy and climate targets for 2050 should consist of a fair share of rule-focused incentives, economic-focused incentives and information-focused incentives. A report related to National Plans of Energy and Climate tackling climate change has been published from the Climate Action Plan [11]. The report stated that an efficient NPEC should include five pillars as follows: a) climate and energy ambitions, b) long term Paris agreement check, c) consistency, d) credibility, and e) transparency. The preliminary Greek National Plan for Energy and Climate has been published by the Greek Ministry of Environment and Climate [2]. The NPEC is a strategic tool presenting an analytical roadmap for the achievement of specific targets in energy and climate up to 2050. It indicates the way to achieve net carbon neutrality in Greece until 2050 in accordance with the international agreement signed in Paris in 2015 for climate change mitigation. The PESTEL methodology regarding productivity enhancement in three economies, in Singapore, Hong Kong and the United Kingdom has been analyzed [8]. The authors stated that the six PESTEL categories were adopted to ensure that the necessary constraints and strategies were comprehensively included. The key barriers to smart cities development in India using PESTEL analysis have been identified [12]. The authors stated that social and political factors are the key barriers to smart cities' development followed by technological and economic factors. They mentioned that environmental and legal factors are less important than the others. The development of renewable energies in Togo using the PESTEL and SWOT methodology has been analyzed [9]. The authors stated that renewable energy development in Togo has improved in the past decade. The proposed methodology has assessed both the internal and external factors related to renewable energy development and its impacts on Togo. A combination of SWOT-PESTEL analysis to examine the challenges faced in schools during Covid-19 pandemic in central Java has been described [13]. The authors selected four aspects in their analysis examining: a) risk management, b) sustainable teaching, c) emergency preparedness, d) educational quality. The use of PEST methodology in strategic analysis has been studied [10]. The authors stated that PEST methodology is an analytical tool which also has systemic characteristics. The methodology of PESTEL analysis has been examined [14]. The author stated that the purpose of PESTEL analysis is to wake you around and see what is happening in the broader external environment. He also mentioned that PESTEL analysis helps to look at all important factors that might affect the success or failure of a project. The use of agrivoltaics has been reviewed [3]. The authors stated that the increased global demand for food and energy implies higher competition for agricultural land. They

also mentioned that electricity and food can be both produced in the same land with the use of agrivoltaics. The use of agrivoltaics has been examined [15]. The authors studied the factors that affect electricity and agricultural production in agrivoltaics systems. They also mentioned that crop yields were reduced by 3% to 62% for more than 80% of the tested crops due to agrivoltaics' use. The energy generation from bifacial photovoltaic modules has been studied [16]. The authors stated that bifacial modules can increase the energy yield by 4% - 15% depending on the module type and the ground. They also mentioned that a constant tilt angle is preferred for reducing the cost of installation and maintenance while the orientation of the bifacial modules affect their energy yield. The benefits of bifacial solar cells in high latitudes have been investigated [17]. The authors stated that bifacial photovoltaics is a rapidly growing technology increasing the electricity generation by using both sides of panels. They also mentioned that at high latitudes vertical photovoltaics can be beneficial due to the low altitude angle enabling them to harvest solar energy for many hours. The floating photovoltaics (FPV) have been reviewed [4]. The authors stated that FPV are becoming a viable option for many countries where the population density increases and land prices rise. They also mentioned that 1% coverage of global reservoirs with FPVs would have a potential capacity of 404 GW_p of green power generation. The floating solar-PV design concepts have been studied [18]. The authors stated that the capital cost of FPVs is higher, at 0.8 – 1.2 \$ per watt peak, compared to similar ground-mounted solar-PV systems. Additionally, they mentioned that several aspects of this technology require further research for understanding better the impacts on water bodies. The semi-transparent building integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) have been reviewed [19]. The authors stated that BIPV have the potential to increase the energy efficiency of buildings. They also mentioned that they can be placed on buildings' facades helping the building to meet its own energy needs with solar energy. The recent advances of perovskite semi-transparent solar photovoltaics have been studied [20]. The authors stated that Perovskite solar cell technology is a low-cost technology with satisfactory energy efficiency. They also mentioned that these solar cells can be placed on the windows and rooftops of buildings meeting their energy requirements. The organic photovoltaic cells have been reviewed [5]. The authors stated that solar cells have low production cost while they can be manufactured in thin and flexible forms. However, they mentioned, they have lower efficiency and short durability. The recent progress in flexible organic photovoltaics has been investigated [21]. The authors stated that organic photovoltaics have achieved efficiencies over 19% in laboratory scale units. They also mentioned that commercial application of organic photovoltaics requires their printing in large-scale modules. The application of photovoltaic systems installed on rooftops of buildings has been reviewed [7]. The authors stated that solar-PVs should be installed preferably in public buildings compared to private buildings. They also mentioned that the main problems in solar-PVs placed on rooftop of buildings are the ash accumulation on the panels and the high temperatures developed in them. The solar-PV systems installed on rooftop of buildings in USA have been assessed [22]. The authors estimated that the total potential power of solar-PV installation in buildings in USA is at 1,118 GW_p while the potential electricity generation is at 1,432 GWh/year. This amount corresponds at 39% of the total power consumption in USA. They also mentioned that they have assumed that the average energy efficiency of solar modules was at 16%. The ground-mounted solar-PV systems have been compared with solar-PVs installed on rooftop of buildings [23]. The authors estimated that the solar-PVs installed on rooftop of buildings have a higher utilization factor by 2.9% and a higher levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) up to 23.7% compared to ground-mounted solar-PVs. The ground-mounted solar-PVs have been compared with solar-PVs installed on rooftop of buildings [6]. The authors stated that both solar-PV configurations have advantages and drawbacks. The impact of ground-mounted solar-PV parks on the cooling of land surface has been studied [24]. The authors stated that ground-mounted solar photovoltaics result in land cooling which extends beyond the solar park boundary. They also mentioned that experimental data in two large solar-PV plants in China and in USA have shown that the land up to 730m away from the boundaries of these solar parks was cooled of up to 2.3°C. The required land area for the installation of several renewable energy systems has been estimated [25]. The report stated that the impact of solar photovoltaics on the landscape is low compared with other energy technologies. It is also mentioned that assuming that the efficiency of flat-plate solar-PV modules is around 10%-20% and their capacity factor at 20% the required land for their installation on the soil varies in the range of 10-50 Km²/GW. The possibility of covering all the power demand in the island of Crete, Greece with solar-PV systems has been investigated [26]. The author stated that solar photovoltaic systems can meet

all the power demand in the island while their investment cost has been estimated at 2,333 euro per permanent resident. He also mentioned that the required land area for installing the necessary solar-PV systems in Crete is at 4,660 ha which corresponds at 0.56% of the total surface of the island. The use of solar-PV systems meeting the power demand in the island of Crete, Greece avoiding land use conflicts has been examined [27]. The author stated that there are several configurations for the installation of solar modules in Crete including: a) conventional mounting on the ground, b) installing them on rooftops and facades of buildings, c) floating them on the surface of water bodies, d) installing vertically bifacial solar modules, and e) use of agrivoltaics. The development of solar-PV systems without using precious land has been examined [28]. The authors stated that there are several alternative ways for installing solar-PVs including: a) the symbiosis of solar modules with agricultural production in the same land area, b) their installation on the surface of water reservoirs, and c) installation on rooftop of buildings. These alternative configurations of installing solar-PV systems allow the use of precious land area for food and animal feed production. The contribution of solar photovoltaic technology in sustainability has been studied [29]. The authors stated that solar-PV technology is currently a highly cost-competitive technology which contributes significantly to CO₂ emissions mitigation. They also mentioned that the share of solar-PV electricity in the global electricity demand was in 2019 at 2.8%. However, they added, having an annual growth rate at around 50% solar-PV technology is expected to have a pivotal role in the global decarbonization by 2050. The role of solar-PV systems in the clean energy transition has been studied [30]. It is stated that solar photovoltaic is a technology that is going to guide decarbonization and the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. It is foreseen that the share of solar-PV electricity in the total power mix globally will be at around 22% by 2050. It is also mentioned that 25% of small-scale solar-PV systems will be installed on rooftops of buildings while the rest 75% of them will be of utility scale. The future of solar-PV technology has been studied [31]. The author stated that the cost of solar-PV modules has decreased substantially the last two decades resulting in the rapid growth of solar photovoltaic installations. He also mentioned that the drop in the cost of solar modules is going to continue while solar-PV electricity is expected to be the leader among benign energy technologies in the green energy transition in the coming decades. The future of solar photovoltaics in a low carbon society has been studied [32]. The study stated that accelerated deployment of renewable energies combined with deep electrification and increased energy efficiency can achieve over 90% of the energy-related CO₂ emissions reduction needed by 2050. It is also mentioned that solar photovoltaics by 2050 would represent the second-largest power generation source generating around 25% of the total electricity demand globally.

THE GREEK NATIONAL PLAN FOR ENERGY AND CLIMATE

The Greek NPEC is the governmental strategic plan for climate and energy issues, setting out a detailed roadmap regarding the attainment of specific energy and climate objectives by 2050. The NPEC sets out and describes priorities and policy measures in respect of a wide range of development and economic activities intended to benefit Greek society, and therefore it is a reference text for the forthcoming decades. It provides a roadmap for substantial reduction in GHG emissions. The core objective is set for 40% reduction in GHG emissions in 2030 compared to 1990, or more than 55% compared to 2005 levels. The policy measures foreseen for GHG emissions reduction and removal include:

- a) Shutdown of lignite-fired power plants and interconnection of the grids of autonomous island systems,
- b) Promoting natural gas as an intermediate fuel for reducing the carbon footprint of the energy system,
- c) Promoting renewable energy sources (RES), storage systems and fuel production from RES,
- d) Improvement in energy efficiency of buildings, industry and infrastructures, and
- e) Reduction in emissions in the transport sector.

With reference the Greek NPEC the electricity generation, the installed power of several renewable energy systems and the electricity storage systems in the country during the period 2025-2050 are

presented in tables 1, 2 and 3 correspondingly. In table 2 is shown that the installed power of solar photovoltaic systems is expected to exceed 50% of the installed power of all the renewable energy systems indicating the pivotal role of solar photovoltaic technology in the green energy transition in Greece. The abovementioned targets might slightly change after the public consultation of the NPEC.

Table 1. Forecast of Electricity Generation in Greece during the Period 2025-2050

	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Electricity generation from RES (TWh)	34.5	53.7	84.4	113.4	156.0	172.3
Total electricity generation (TWh)	57.0	65.6	86.8	113.4	156.4	173.7
Electricity generation from RES to total electricity generation (%)	60.53	81.86	97.24	100	99.74	99.77

Source: The Greek NPEC, 2023

Table 2. Forecast of the Installed Power of Several Renewable Energy Systems in the Period 2025-2050 in Greece (GW)

Technology	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
On-shore wind farms	6.0	9.5	8.5	9.2	11.8	11.9
Off-shore wind farms	-	-	6.2	9.8	15.4	17.3
Solar-PV	8.2	13.4	18.7	25.4	35.2	40.3
Hydropower	3.1	3.8	3.8	3.8	3.8	3.9
Other RES including biogas, et cetera	0.5	0.6	1.3	1.8	2.0	2.1
Total RES systems	17.8	27.3	38.5	50	68.2	75.5
Solar-PV power to total power of RES (%)	46.07%	49.08%	48.57%	50.80%	51.61%	53.38%

Source: The Greek NPEC, 2023

Table 3. Forecast of the Power of Electricity Storage Systems in Greece in the Period 2025-2050

	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Electric batteries (GW)	1.9	3.1	3.6	8.8	19.1	22.6
Pumped-hydro storage systems (GW)	1.4	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2
Total power of electricity storage systems (GW)	3.3	5.3	5.8	11.0	21.3	24.8
Total power of electricity storage to total power of installed RES (%)	18.54%	19.41%	15.06%	21.65%	31.23%	46.46%
Total power of electricity storage systems to total power of installed Solar-PV systems (%)	40.24%	39.55%	31.02%	43.31%	60.51%	61.54%

Source: The Greek NPEC, 2023

DIFFERENT TYPES OF SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAICS THAT CAN BE USED FOR POWER GENERATION IN GREECE

Solar photovoltaics and off-shore wind turbines are prioritized as the key benign energy technologies for achieving the target of net-zero emissions in 2050 in Greece while the installed power of solar photovoltaic systems is foreseen to be more than double the size off-shore wind turbines (table 2). Several types of solar-PV systems installed in different configurations can be used in Greece. The most of them are currently commercialized. They include:

Conventional Solar-PV Installed on the Ground

Solar photovoltaic systems are installed to day mainly on the ground. The availability and the cost of land are important factors for choosing the best installation option. Installation of solar photovoltaics on fertile land areas might create local protests and conflicts. The ground-mounted solar-PV systems are easily installed, have lower maintenance cost while they are easily accessible. Installation of

solar-PV systems on the ground have many advantages compared to other configurations such as installation on rooftop of buildings or their floating on the surface of water reservoirs.

Installation on Rooftops and Facades of Buildings

Solar photovoltaic modules can be placed on rooftops of private and public buildings due to ample solar radiation. Buildings roofs have very good properties for the installation of PV modules. Public buildings and offices should be preferred for installation of solar PV modules due to the fact that they operate during the day time when solar electricity is harvested. The generated electricity can meet part or all of the energy requirements while any excess electricity can be stored into the grid. The solar irradiance in the building roofs is high, the ventilation conditions are good and the solar modules can be placed flexibly in the desired tilt angle. Occasionally, in cities, part of building roofs might have increased shading from nearby located buildings. The generated solar electricity is utilized on-site while the grid connection already exists. Installation of solar-PVs on rooftop of buildings reduces the temperature of the building roof which might be beneficial when the buildings are located near the equator having high cooling loads. Installation of solar-PVs on building roofs is often preferable than their installation on the ground which might create conflicts related to alternative land uses.

Agrivoltaics

Agrivoltaics are solar-PV systems installed in land areas combining agricultural production and power generation. Several experimental studies have been implemented so far trying to optimize simultaneously electricity generation and crops yield altering several parameters like the type of solar modules used, their elevation, the tilt angle and the spacing of the modules. However, it has been reported that in many experimental agrivoltaic systems the crop yields have been reduced by 3% to 62%. The cost of agrivoltaics is 20%-30% higher than the cost of conventional solar-PV systems which though is compensated from their advantages.

Floating Photovoltaics

Floating photovoltaics are solar-PV systems which are installed on the surface of water bodies including natural lakes and man-made water reservoirs. Floating PV systems are a preferable option in the cases of low availability of land and when the cost of land is very high. It is a rapidly growing technology with many commercial applications in Asian countries having various advantages and drawbacks. The main advantages of floating photovoltaics are related with higher energy yields compared to conventional PVs and the decrease of water evaporation in water reservoirs. The main drawbacks are related with their higher cost compared to conventional solar-PVs and their impact on water quality and on living organisms in water bodies which are not fully understood.

Bifacial Solar Modules

Bifacial solar-PV systems consist of a rapidly grown technology. Bifacial PV modules can capture and utilize solar radiation on both surfaces. They have higher electricity yields than conventional solar-PV in the range of 4% to 15% with an average at 9%. They can be installed either on the ground or in buildings while they can be installed vertically minimizing the use of valuable land area. Their higher installation cost is offset by their multiple benefits compared to conventional solar-PV systems.

Semi-Transparent Solar-PV Modules

Semi-transparent solar-PV systems allow part of the solar irradiance to penetrate the solar modules which is beneficial in many applications. They can be used in buildings and in agricultural greenhouses generating electricity which is mainly consumed on-site while the solar radiation going through the modules is properly used. The use of semi-transparent solar modules in buildings' facades is complementary to installation of opaque solar modules while both of them can meet part or all of their power needs. The cost of semi-transparent solar modules is higher than the cost of conventional opaque solar-PVs while the higher cost is counterbalanced by the multiple benefits.

Organic Photovoltaics

Organic photovoltaics are manufactured from organic materials while the conventional photovoltaics are produced by inorganic compounds like silicon. Organic PVs can be produced as thin and flexible solar cells while their production cost is low. However, they have lower efficiency and durability

compared to silicon-based solar modules. The commercial application of organic photovoltaics requires their production in large scale printing systems. The advantages related to future development of solar-PV systems in Greece are presented in table 4.

Table 4. Advantages Related with the Future Development of Solar-PV Systems in Greece

1	Low-cost of solar-PV modules
2	High solar radiation in Greece
3	Easy installation
4	Low maintenance cost
5	Solar-PV systems are easily accepted in local communities compared to other RES systems
6	They can be installed on rooftops and facades of buildings allowing the self-consumption of the generated electricity
7	They promote the distributed generation of power
8	Households and SMEs can benefit from solar-PV technology installing solar modules at their premises meeting their electricity consumption becoming “energy procurers”
9	Owners of electric vehicles can recharge the electric batteries with green electricity generated with solar-PV panels installed at their residential buildings
10	Solar-PV systems can be installed in several configurations such as rooftops and facades of buildings, agricultural land and water reservoirs
11	Power generation does not produce on-site emissions

The required land area for the installation of several renewable energy technologies is presented in table 5.

Table 5. Required Land Area for the Installation of Several Renewable Energy Technologies

Technology	Conversion efficiency (%)	Capacity factor (%)	Required land area (Km ² /GW)	Required land area (m ² /GWh)
Flat-plate solar-PV systems	10%-20%	20 %	10-50	5,000-25,000
Wind turbines	Low to 20%	20 %	100	140,000
Biomass burning	75-85%	-	1,000	500,000
Solar thermal systems	15%-25%	25 %	20-50	10,000-20,000

Source: [26]

Taking into account that the total area in Greece is 131,957 Km², the average annual solar-PV generation is 1,400 KWh per KW_p and assuming that the required land area for the installation of flat plate solar-PV systems is at 30 Km²/GW [26] the required land area in Greece for the installation of solar-PV systems and the solar-PV power generation compared to the total electricity generation in Greece according to the NPEC are presented in table 6.

Table 6. Required Land Area in Greece for the Installation of Solar-PV Systems According to the National Plan for Energy and Climate

	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Installed power of solar-PV systems (GW)	8.2	13.4	18.7	25.4	35.2	40.3
Required land area (Km ²)	246	402	561	762	1,056	1,209
Required land area for solar-PV to total Greek area (%)	0.19	0.30	0.43	0.58	0.80	0.92
Annual solar electricity generation (TWh)	11.5	18.8	26.2	35.6	49.3	56.4
Solar-PV electricity generation to total energy consumption (%)	20.18	28.66	30.18	31.42	31.52	32.47

Source: own estimations

THE IMPACT OF EXTERNAL FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN GREECE UP TO 2050 – PESTEL ANALYSIS

PESTEL analysis is a useful tool for the identification of the external macro-economic forces which might influence an organization or a project. The six letters in the acronym represent the political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors of the external environment which might affect positively or negatively a project or an organization in achieving its goals. The external factors which might influence the achievement of the goals in the Greek NPEC are analyzed below.

Political Factors

The change in the Greek, European or International policies regarding the green energy transition, according to the international agreement for climate change mitigation signed in Paris in 2015, might affect the development of solar-PV systems in Greece and the fulfillment of the targets set in the NPEC. The high cost of energy and fuels combined with the required high capital investments for the promotion of solar-PV and other renewable energy technologies as well as for modernizing the electric grid might result in reactions and protests in local communities. Many people want to allocate and invest the available funds in social services for the benefit of the society. This does not favor the promotion of RES and the development of solar-PV systems in Greece. The unwillingness and protests of citizens in Greece regarding the green energy transition, according to Paris agreement, might delay the development of solar-PV systems in the country and the achievement of the desired targets.

Economic Factors

Changes in the capital cost of solar-PV systems as well as in the capital cost of other energy technologies may affect positively or negatively their development. These changes may increase or decrease the attractiveness and the profitability of solar-PV systems. Future energy crisis which probably are going to increase the cost of fossil fuels and electricity will increase the attractiveness and competitiveness of solar-PV systems. Increase in the price of carbon credits is also going to increase the competitiveness of solar-PV systems compared to various conventional energy technologies.

Social Factors

Various social factors may affect the development of solar photovoltaics in Greece. The positive or negative perception of local societies to solar-PV technology may affect the development of solar photovoltaic systems. Additionally, the willingness of local societies to create energy cooperatives, which often invest in solar electricity generation, may increase the development of solar-PV systems in Greece. The competition regarding the land use for food production and electricity generation may result in local protests and conflicts particularly in fertile land areas. These conflicts may delay the development of solar-PV systems in the country.

Technological Factors

Several technological improvements in the solar photovoltaic technology as well as in other benign energy technologies may facilitate or make more difficult the development of solar-PV technology in Greece. The commercial development of organic photovoltaics, of bifacial photovoltaics, of agrivoltaics, of semi-transparent photovoltaics et cetera may accelerate or decelerate the growth of solar-PV in Greece. Technological improvements in other benign energy technologies such as electric batteries, atmospheric carbon capture, et cetera may have positive or negative impacts on the development of solar-PV systems.

Environmental Factors

Several environmental factors might have positive or negative impacts in the growth of solar-PV systems in Greece. Installation of floating solar-PVs in water bodies might delay if future studies indicate that their impacts on water quality and on living organisms are remarkable.

Legal Factors

Changes in environmental regulations and legislation might have positive or negative impacts on the growth of solar-PV in Greece. New environmental regulations regarding the maximum permitted

emissions from power plants might limit the use of fossil fuel-electricity generation resulting in faster growth of solar-PVs. New environmental legislation regarding the recycle of used solar modules might increase the cost of solar electricity. Changes in environmental legislation regarding the installation of opaque solar-PVs on the soil might delay the growth of solar-PVs in Greece. The obligatory installation of solar-PVs in buildings for meeting their electricity load might increase their use for power generation in residential, public and hotel buildings. The development of attractive legislation regarding the installation of floating solar-PV on water reservoirs might affect positively the development of FPV in Greece.

DISCUSSION

The role of solar-PV electricity in the clean energy transition in Greece in 2050 according to the NPEC has been studied. The solar modules can be installed in several configurations depending on the local conditions and priorities. Various external factors might affect positively or negatively the development of solar photovoltaics in the country in the coming decades. The high solar radiation in Greece and the low cost of solar-PV modules favor their use in electricity generation. The cost of solar electricity is low and competitive to power generation from other fossil or renewable fuels. This is why the solar-PV installations are growing rapidly in the country. A significant advantage of solar-PV systems compared to wind parks is their acceptance from local communities. Wind parks are not easily accepted by local societies who often protest and delay the implementation of wind energy investments. Additionally, households and small and medium enterprises can invest in small- or medium-size solar-PV systems meeting their power needs becoming “prosumers”.

The solar-PV electricity in 2050 in Greece is foreseen to have a share at 32.47% of the total electricity mix. This is higher than the global share of solar-PV electricity predicted in other studies at 22%-25% [31], [33]. The most of solar-PV systems in Greece are placed on rooftop of buildings and are mounted on the soil. New configurations of solar modules are going to be developed in the future including photovoltaics floating on surface of water bodies, agrivoltaics allowing the simultaneous production of food and electricity, vertical bifacial photovoltaics and semi-transparent photovoltaics integrated in buildings' envelope. These novel configurations of solar modules have various advantages compared to conventional configurations used so far. Acceleration in the development of solar-PV systems in Greece can be achieved with the increase of the electricity storage capacity in the country. This requires investments in large-scale electric batteries or in pumped-hydro storage systems. Additionally, the upgrading of the old electric grid in the country is necessary.

Our work and the accuracy of our results is based on the assumptions and the data provided in the provisional NPEC until 2050. These assumptions might change after the public consultation of the NPEC and our results might change as well. Further work should be focused on the estimation of the electricity storage capacity which is necessary to support the development of solar-PV systems and wind parks in the next 25 years in Greece according to the NPEC.

CONCLUSIONS

The development of solar-PV systems in Greece according to the roadmap proposed in the NPEC has been studied. Additionally, the impacts of several external factors which could affect the solar photovoltaic development have been analyzed. The Greek NPEC foresees that in 2050 the installed power of solar-PV systems in the country will be higher than 50% of the total installed power of renewable energy systems. Therefore, the role of solar-PV systems is going to be pivotal in the clean energy transition by 2050. The solar photovoltaic systems can be installed in various configurations including their installation on the ground, floating on the surface of water bodies and on rooftops or in facades of buildings. The required land area for the installation of solar-PV systems in 2050 in Greece according to the NPEC is estimated at 0.92% of the total area of the country, while the solar-PV electricity generation corresponds at 32.47% of the total electricity demand in Greece in 2050. Several external factors categorized as political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal might affect positively or negatively the development of solar-PV systems in Greece in the coming decades. Our study indicates that solar-PV energy is going to play an important role in the clean energy transition in Greece until 2050. Therefore, the development of appropriate policies and measures is necessary to facilitate the penetration of solar-PVs in the Greek energy system.

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